

Addition Compounds of Organotin Halides-IV. Adducts of Triphenyl Tinchloride and Diphenyl Tin Dichloride with Amines

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Complexes of triphenyl tin chloride and diphenyl tin dichloride with bases as pyridine, α -, β -, γ -picolines, isoquinoline, piperidine, morpholine, aniline and benzylamine have been prepared and characterised by their molar conductance and i.r. studies.

Extensive work on the addition complexes of organotin halides has been carried out^{1,2}, and we investigated the addition complexes of tri(*n*-propyl) tin chloride, di (*n*-propyl) tin dichloride and *n*-propyl tin trichloride³⁻⁵. We now report the studies of complexes of triphenyl tin chloride and diphenyl tin dichloride with amines. Some work on the complexes of these organotin halides had already been reported⁶⁻⁸, and we have prepared and studied the complexes of these two Lewis acids with bases such as pyridine, α -, β -, γ -picolines, isoquinoline, piperidine, morpholine, aniline and benzylamine.

EXPERIMENTAL

Triphenyl tin chloride and diphenyl tin dichloride were prepared by refluxing tetraphenyl tin and tin tetra chloride in calculated amounts at specified temperatures^{9,10} and purified by repeated crystallizations from dry diethyl ether.

The complexes were prepared by mixing excess of freshly distilled amine with known quantities of the respective phenyl tin halides (both taken in dry petroleum ether). The resulting white solid products were washed with excess of dry petroleum ether, dried under vacuum and analysed for their tin and halogen contents to establish their stoichiometry.

The molar conductance values of these complexes were studied by measuring the conductances of millimolar solutions of these complexes in nitrobenzene on a Toshniwal conductometric bridge at 25°.

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The i.r. spectra of these complexes were scanned as KBr discs on a Perkin Elmer 337 grating spectrophotometer.

A brief description of all these complexes has been recorded in Tables I and II respectively.

DISCUSSION

Triphenyl tin chloride, (Ph_3SnCl) forms two types of complexes, $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}\cdot\text{L}$, where L is isoquinoline, piperidine or benzylamine and $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}\cdot\text{L}_2$ where L is pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline or morpholine. The molar conductance values of these complexes, in nitrobenzene, are below $10 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$, indicating thereby that they do not ionize in nitrobenzene (Table I).

TABLE I
Complexes of Triphenyl Tin Chloride with Bases

Sr. No.	Base	m.pt. (°C)	Stoichiometry Base : Ph_3SnCl	Molar Conductance $\text{cm}^2 \text{ ohm}^{-1}$ mole^{-1}	% of tin		% of Cl	
					Required	Found	Required	Found
1.	Pyridine	82	2 : 1	0.673	21.89	22.10	6.53	6.65
2.	β -Picoline	83—84	2 : 1	1.314	20.82	20.56	6.21	6.01
3.	γ -Picoline	145—146	2 : 1	8.917	20.82	20.75	6.21	6.54
4.	Isoquinoline	110	1 : 1	6.337	23.12	23.00	6.89	6.57
5.	Piperidine	above 250	1 : 1	$*0.06 \times 10^{-4}$	25.29	25.19	7.54	7.35
6.	Morpholine	160 (decomposed)	2 : 1	4.570	21.26	21.83	6.34	6.45
7.	Aniline	102—104	?	$*0.37 \times 10^{-5}$	20.82	—	6.21 (for 2 : 1)	14.01
8.	Benzylamine	above 250	1 : 1	$*0.06 \times 10^{-5}$	24.17	24.14	7.20	7.89

* Specific conductance values of suspensions in nitrobenzene.

The complexes, $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}\cdot\text{L}$, as recorded in other similar cases¹¹, have trigonal bipyramidal structure with pentacoordinated tin. The complexes, $\text{Ph}_3\text{SnCl}\cdot\text{L}_2$ are octahedral with hexa-coordinated tin².

Diphenyl tin dichloride, as is obvious from Table II forms the complexes, $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}_2$, with isoquinoline, aniline and benzylamine and $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}_4$ with pyridine, α -, β -, γ -picolines, piperidine and morpholine. The former possess octahedral structure with hexa-coordinated tin and the latter in those cases where all the base molecules coordinate, have distorted cubic structure with eight coordinated tin in the centre of the cube¹².

Whereas the octahedral structure in case of $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}_2$ seems to be quite appropriate, that of $\text{Ph}_2\text{SnCl}_2\cdot\text{L}_4$ may have two possibilities. The first is octahedral in which only two molecules of the base are coordinated to tin and the remaining two molecules are probably accommodated in the crystal lattice of the octahedron. The second is that in which all the four molecules of the base are linked to tin through coordination.

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The i.r. studies help in arriving at the correct structure. Two frequencies at 605 cm^{-1} and 405 cm^{-1} associated with pyridine molecule must increase in the complex in which there is coordination link between tin and pyridine. If the first possibility is correct, the spectra of the complex should show two frequencies at 605 and 405 cm^{-1} corresponding to the uncoordinated pyridine molecules and two higher frequencies corresponding to the coordinated pyridine molecules¹³. But in case of second possibility only two higher frequencies should occur. The actual data which shows only two frequencies at 630 cm^{-1} and 435 cm^{-1} suggest that all the base molecules are coordinating and tin may be in octa-coordination state.

All the complexes of diphenyl tin dichloride except those of α -, β -, γ -picolines give molar conductance values below $10\text{ cm}^2\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{mole}^{-1}$ (Table II). Specific conductance values in case of complexes of piperidine, morpholine, aniline and benzylamine, which are only partially soluble in nitrobenzene, fall in 10^{-5} range. This shows that these complexes do not ionize in the nitrobenzene solutions.

TABLE II

Complexes of Diphenyl tin dichloride with Bases

Sr.No.	Base	m.pt. (°C)	Stoichiometry Base : Ph ₂ SnCl ₂	Molar conductance cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹	% of tin		% of Cl	
					Required	Found	Required	Found
1.	Pyridine	135 (decomposes)	4 : 1	2.23	18.03	17.54	10.76	10.44
2.	α -Picoline	122	4 : 1	11.71	16.62	16.25	9.91	9.83
3.	β -Picoline	128—130	4 : 1	11.01	16.62	15.95	9.91	10.23
4.	γ -Picoline	192—195	4 : 1	10.29	16.62	16.03	9.91	9.80
5.	Isoquinoline	169 (decomposes)	2 : 1	6.76	19.76	19.02	11.79	11.27
6.	Piperidine	165 (decomposes)	4 : 1	* 0.278×10^{-5}	17.40	18.20	10.38	10.56
7.	Morpholine	185 (decomposes)	4 : 1	* 0.510×10^{-5}	17.45	17.00	10.26	9.93
8.	Aniline	106—103	2 : 1	* 0.390×10^{-5}	22.45	22.16	13.39	13.00
9.	Benzylamine	195—200	2 : 1	* 0.440×10^{-5}	21.32	29.64	12.52	12.55

* Specific conductance values of suspensions in nitrobenzene.

Molar conductance values of complexes of α -picoline, β -picoline and γ -picoline though slightly above $10\text{ cm}^2\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{mole}^{-1}$ also do not fall in the range specified for uni-univalent electrolytes. But they do indicate possibility of some ionization⁶ and hence hepta-coordinated tin in the ions as shown below :—

	Molar conductance
(4 α -Picoline Ph ₂ SnCl) ⁺ Cl ⁻	11.71 cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
(4 β -Picoline Ph ₂ SnCl) ⁺ Cl ⁻	11.01 cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹
(4 γ -Picoline Ph ₂ SnCl) ⁺ Cl ⁻	10.29 cm ² ohm ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹

The infra-red spectra of these complexes have been studied in the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} . As the frequencies associated with Sn-Ph, Sn-Cl and Sn \leftarrow N bonds fall in the region below 400 cm^{-1} , which is still under investigation, only the changes arising as a result of coordination in the spectra of bases can be discussed.

Involvement of nitrogen in the formation of co-ordination links results in appreciable increase in C = C and C = N frequencies¹⁴. In the present case, however, the ligand vibrations cannot be distinguished from those of the phenyl groups in the organotin halides and as such, therefore, the assignments cannot be quite clear.

In the pyridine complexes, the two frequencies at 605 cm^{-1} and 405 cm^{-1} , associated with pyridine, increase to 615 cm^{-1} and 425 cm^{-1} in Ph_3SnCl complex and to 630 cm^{-1} and 435 cm^{-1} in Ph_2SnCl_2 complex, which suggests coordination of the pyridine in the complexes.

N-H Frequencies: In primary and secondary amines, when nitrogen forms a coordination link, the N-H frequencies fall and H-N-C deformations increase¹⁴. This effect is further enhanced by an additional hydrogen bond, N-H...Cl, between hydrogen of the N-H group and Cl of the organotin halides. The overall effect of these factors leads to an appreciable decrease in the N-H frequency or in other words weakens the bond.

The i.r. data are recorded as under :—

	$\nu(\text{N-H})\text{cm}^{-1}$	$\delta(\text{N-H})\text{cm}^{-1}$	(H-N-C) deformations cm^{-1}
Piperidine	3291 m	1650 m	822 m
Ph_3SnCl -Piperidine	3160 m	1575 s	850 m
Ph_2SnCl_2 -4 Piperidine	3150 w	1580 s	860 m
Morpholine	3400 w, 3340 s	1675 s	830 s
Ph_3SnCl -2 Morpholine	3375 m	1560 m	860 s
Ph_2SnCl_2 -4 Morpholine	3380 m, 3270 m	1550 s	865 s
Aniline	3390 m, 3315 m	1610 m	
Ph_3SnCl -Aniline	3375 w	1590 m, 1570 m	
Ph_2SnCl_2 -4 Aniline	3240 m, 3190 m	1585 s, 1555 m	
Benzylamine	3330 m, 3250 m	1620 m	850 m ?
Ph_3SnCl -Benzylamine	—	1580 m	870 m
Ph_2SnCl_2 -2 Benzylamine	—	1575 m	870 m

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